

Structural and Fungicidal Studies of Thiazoline Metal Complexes

HERJINDER KAUR^a and S. K. SANGAL^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, N. A. S. (P. G.) College, Meerut-250 002

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

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Thiazolines and their complexes possess various pharmacological properties¹. We report here Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with thiazoline and their fungicidal activity has been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis reveals formation of 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes except in the case of the Fe^{III} complexes where it shows 1 : 3 stoichiometry. The Ni^{II} complexes contain two molecules of coordinated water while the nitrate complexes of Fe^{III} comprise one aqua-ligand. The Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are anhydrous. The hydrated complexes do not lose water even after prolonged desiccation (1 week) under vacuum. Heating at 100–10^o resulted in partial decomposition. Molar conductance values of these complexes (10⁻³M in nitrobenzene) at room temperature are too small ($\Lambda_M \sim 10\text{--}20 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$), indicating their non-ionic nature.

The participation of ring-S in coordination during complexation is indicated by the shifts in the stretching frequencies at 1 530, 1 490 and 1 400 cm⁻¹ assignable to thiazole ring. The main ir bands of the ligand lie at 1 625 (C=C), 3 090 (CH) and 1 690 cm⁻¹ (conjugated cyclic system -C=C-N-C-) respectively. The ν_{CN} band at 1 635 cm⁻¹ remains unchanged during complexation. Comparison of the spectra of the metal complexes with that of ligand shows that the frequency associated with (C-S) stretching mode shifts to lower range by 10–25 cm⁻¹

giving an indication of the coordination of ring-S atom with the metal ion. In all the complexes the vibrational modes due to (M-S) coordination were observed at 280–300 cm⁻¹.

Metal-halogen stretching frequencies appearing at 260–295 cm⁻¹ in the Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} halide complexes are in good agreement for the hexacoordinated metal-halide complex², while the Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes showing band at ~ 295 cm⁻¹ indicate the coordination of chloride ion to the metal.

In the acetato complexes ν_{as} (COO) and ν_{s} (COO) stretching vibrations occur at 1 560 and 1 440 cm⁻¹ respectively. The separation ($\Delta\nu$ 120 cm⁻¹) of these two bands is diagnostic of unidentate carboxylate coordination³ of acetate group through its C-O⁻ moiety.

The nitrate complexes of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} show bands at 1 395–1 430, ~ 1 310, 990–1 010, and 810–825 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{as} (NO₂), ν_{s} (NO₂), NO stretch and out-of-plane NO₂ rocking vibrations respectively. The separation of frequencies by 150 cm⁻¹ indicates monodentate coordination of the nitrate group⁴.

The Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes have magnetic moments in the range 5.62–5.65 and ~ 2.80–3.10 B.M. respectively, suggesting the formation of octahedral complexes⁵. The observed values of magnetic moments of the Co^{II} complexes lie in the range the 4.40–4.45 B.M. expected for

tetrahedral symmetry⁶, while the Cu^{II} complexes show magnetic moment (1.50–1.52 B.M.) slightly lower than the spin-only value. The sub-normal magnetic moments may be due to antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between the adjacent Cu^{II} ions.

The electronic spectra of the Fe^{III} complexes show bands at 8 600 and 10 500 cm⁻¹ which are split components of ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g transition. The splitting of ⁵E_g state may be due to Jahn-Teller distortion.

The Co^{II} complexes show bands at ~19 000–19 200, 16 000, 8 800 and 7 000 cm⁻¹ due to three spin-allowed transitions, ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₂ (ν₁), ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (F) (ν₂) and ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (P) (ν₃) respectively in conformity with spectra of other tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes⁶. The band at 7 000–8 800 and 16 000–19 200 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the split components of ν₂ and ν₃ respectively.

The Ni^{II} complexes have three spin-allowed transitions, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} at ~ 8 400–8 700, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) at 14 000–14 050 and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P) at 24 000–24 120 cm⁻¹ typical of octahedral coordination⁵.

The Cu^{II} complexes exhibit bands at ~ 15 300–15 550 and 19 000 cm⁻¹ attributable to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions respectively, in a square-planar field.

Fungicidal screening : Fungicidal activity of thiazoline complexes (at concentrations 500, 200 and 100 ppm) were evaluated against *Drechslera tetramera*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by growth method⁷. Thiazoline compounds possess good fungicidal property due to the presence of >N–C–S– grouping as well as phenyl groups⁸. Toxicological data indicate that there exist a gradual decline of growth with the increasing dose of metal complexes. The average percentage inhibition at 500 ppm level for all the complexes are as follows : *D. tetramera* (75–60%), *A. alternata* (75–61%), *F. oxysporum* (75–60%); the corresponding figures for the ligand are 91, 81 and 91%. The toxicity

of metal ions follows the order : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Fe^{III}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. make. Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Beckmann 20 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a CZ-specord spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method using Hg[Co-(CNS)₄] as calibrant. The stoichiometry was established through the analyses of metal, anion and sulphur by standard procedure⁹.

The ligand PhImeT was prepared following the literature method¹⁰.

Fe^{III} complexes : A mixture of the ligand (0.03 mol) and Fe^{III} salts (0.01 mol) dissolved in hot EtOH (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h with stirring, then concentrated and kept overnight. The precipitate that separated was washed with EtOH, ether, and dried.

Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes : Solutions of metal^{II} salts (0.01 mol) in dry EtOH (15 ml) were added to EtOH solution (20 ml) the ligand (0.02 mol). The pH of the reaction mixture was slightly raised (6 to 9) by dropwise addition of ammonia and then it was refluxed for 1 h. The product obtained, was filtered, washed with EtOH and dried.

Ni^{II} complexes : Ni^{II} salt (0.01 mol) was added to a refluxing solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) in EtOH followed by the addition of alcoholic solution of sodium acetate (15 ml). The contents were refluxed for 1 h, then concentrated to half of the volume and the resulting solid was washed with EtOH, ether and dried.

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NOTE

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